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The Development and Psychometric Evaluation of the Objectification Perpetration Scale

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While the literature has shown that sexually objectifying women leads to negative outcomes for the target and perceiver, measures of objectification perpetration are often adaptations of measures designed to assess targets' self-objectification or reported experiences of objectifying behaviors. In the present article, we introduce the Objectification Perpetration Scale (OPS) that assesses not only men's perpetration of objectifying behaviors directed toward women but also their objectifying cognitions and beliefs. Data from 855 men were collected across two studies. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in the first sample revealed two distinct factors and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in the second, independent sample, supported the factor structure of the newly developed 16-item OPS, including: sex-based (10 items) and appearance-based (6 items) objectification perpetration. Supporting its construct validity, scores on the OPS and the subscales were positively associated with scores on other measures of objectification perpetration, measures of sexual violence perpetration, and sexual exchange and misogynistic ideologies. The OPS contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the objectification perpetration phenomenon, including objectification that reduces women to either their sexual appeal or appearance.

Keywords: objectification, sexualization, social perception, social cognition

Sexual objectification occurs when a person, typically a woman, is treated as a sexual thing, rather than a fellow human being. More specifically, when a woman is reduced to her appearance or sexual body parts and functions for the use of a man, she is said to be objectified (Bartky, 1990; Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). Sexual objectification fundamentally alters how women are perceived. When sexually objectified, women are dehumanized—they are seen as lacking warmth and competence (Heflick & Goldenberg, 2009), lacking agency and moral patency (Loughnan et al., 2010), and likened to animals (Vaes et al., 2011) and objects (Bernard et al., 2012; Gervais et al., 2012; Rudman & Mescher, 2012). Such dehumanization paves the way for violence perpetration. When men objectify women, they are more likely to accept violence directed toward women (Loughnan et al., 2013), increase their propensity toward sexual violence (Rudman & Mescher, 2012), and actually sexually aggress against women (Gervais et al., 2014). Understanding men who perpetrate objectification toward women is a first step toward preventing its occurrence. Toward this end, the purpose of the present research was to develop and validate a new measure of objectification perpetration.

In the present work, we developed the Objectification Perpetration Scale (OPS). The OPS was developed by a panel of experts based on theorizing regarding the central facets of objectification (Langton, 2009; Morris et al., 2018; Nussbaum, 1995). While men are sometimes objectified and women sometimes objectify, research suggests that men most frequently objectify women (Gervais et al., 2018). Thus, in our initial investigation of the OPS, we focused on men's objectification of women. Specifically, the purpose of the present work was threefold:

(a) develop a measure of objectifying attitudes (including cognitions, motivations, and behaviors); (b) explore and confirm the factor structure of the OPS; and (c) consider the construct validity of the OPS, examining the relations between objectification attitudes and constructs that ought to be closely related as derived from objectification theory (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997) and related research (Bernard et al., 2018; Roberts et al., 2018).

Objectification Theory

Feminist scholars have long argued that women are sexually objectified by men to create, reinforce, and maintain patriarchy (Bartky, 1990; deBeauvoir, 1949; Dworkin, 1991; Langton, 2009; LeMoncheck, 1985; MacKinnon, 1987; Nussbaum, 1995). Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) provided a psychological theory through which to understand the causes and consequences of objectification. Specifically, they suggest that Western cultures are marked by pervasive heterosexuality in which men and women alike receive messages that women are sex objects. These messages are most often conveyed through the male gaze depicted in mainstream media (e.g., when the camera focuses on women's sexual body parts, when men are depicted as ogling women's bodies) and interpersonal interactions (e.g., objectifying gazes, appearance commentary). According to Objectification Theory (1997), this objectifying environment causes women to objectify themselves, providing the foundation for short-term (e.g., increased anxiety, reduced flow) and long-term (e.g., sexual dysfunction, disordered eating behaviors) mental health problems. In support of objectification theory, a plethora of studies have since revealed myriad consequences of women's internalization of objectifying perspectives, affecting women's health, physicality, cognitions, behaviors, motivations, affect, social behaviors, and interactions (see Roberts et al., 2018, for a review). In light of this literature, it is necessary to distinguish between the ways in which women are behaviorally and cognitively objectified.

While objectification theory primarily focused on self-objectification and its consequences, it also inspired studies examining the consequences of men's sexual objectification perpetration (e.g., Bernard et al., 2018; Roberts et al., 2018). For instance, research has linked viewing women as sexual objects with increased dehumanization of women (Haslam, 2006), and more specifically, lower attributions of competence, agency, and moral patency of women (Heflick et al., 2011; Heflick &

Goldenberg, 2009; Wollast et al., 2018). Additionally, men's objectification of their romantic partner (Doran & Price, 2014; Wright & Tokunaga, 2016; Zurbriggen et al., 2011) and women more generally (Sáez et al., 2019), diminishes men's relationship satisfaction. Together, objectification perpetration and perceptions of women as less than human sets the foundation for violence; men who objectify women are more likely to hold positive attitudes toward violence against women (Wright & Tokunaga, 2016), perpetrate sexual aggression (Franz et al., 2018; Gervais et al., 2014; Mikorski & Szymanski, 2017; Sáez et al., 2019), use sexual coercion (Ramsey & Hoyt, 2015), and perpetrate intimate partner violence (Jonsson et al., 2018; Sáez et al., 2020). Despite these consequences, a comprehensive understanding of when and why men objectify women remains underdeveloped.

One of the reasons for this dearth in the research is due to inconsistencies in conceptualizations of objectification perpetration (e.g., cognitively, behaviorally, as a focus on sex appeal, or appearance more broadly). For example, within experimental research, manipulations of objectifying perspectives often involve either exposure to sexualized versus clothed women (Cikara et al., 2011; Loughnan et al., 2013; Wollast et al., 2018) or promoting a focus on women's appearance versus personality (Bernard et al., 2015; Heflick et al., 2011; Heflick & Goldenberg, 2009; Riemer et al., 2018). While these manipulations rely on similar approaches to drawing attention to women's bodies, the focus here may be shifting from sex-based objectification (in studies manipulating exposure to scantily clad women) to appearance-based objectification (in studies promoting a focus on women's appearance more generally), potentially resulting in different outcomes. Moreover, the nature of a control condition is also affected by these conceptualizations; while women's appearance is not encapsulated in participants' focus on a woman's personality (relative to appearance), a control condition in which participants focus on the appearance of a clothed (relative to scantily clad or nude) woman may still involve objectification. In studies in which objectification perpetration has been measured, few assessments begin with men's experiences of perpetrating objectification. For instance, the traditional approach to objectification perpetration measurement has been to modify existing measures of self-objectification to assess objectification of other people. Strelan and Hargreaves (2005), for example, modified the Self-Objectification Questionnaire (SOQ; Noll & Fredrickson, 1998) to create the Other-Objectification Questionnaire—Woman version (OOQ-W). The OOQ-W assesses the degree to which women's observable physical appearance attributes (e.g., weight, sex appeal) are valued relative to women's nonobservable physical attributes (e.g., strength, stamina). While a strong conceptualization of objectification, men's objectification of women may occur through a different cognitive process or involve consideration of distinctly different attributes (e.g., sexual availability). Moreover, the SOQ and its subsequent adaptations (e.g., the OOQ-W) have important limitations including poor reliability and a consistently high proportion of participants who misunderstand the scaling format (Wollast et al., 2021). Another common approach to assessing objectification perpetration involves modification of existing measures of women's interpersonal experiences of objectification. Gervais et al. (2018), for example, modified the Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale (ISOS; Kozee et al., 2007) to create a perpetration version (Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale—Perpetration version [ISOS-P]). In the perpetrator version of the ISOS, participants are asked to indicate how frequently they engage in body evaluations (BE) and unwanted sexual advances (USA) toward women. Within this approach, researchers assume that the interpersonal experiences of objectification that women not only experience, but also notice, are a comprehensive representation of the ways in which men perpetrate objectification. Together, these approaches (e.g., Gervais et al., 2018; Strelan & Hargreaves, 2005; Zurbriggen et al., 2011) use women's experiences of objectification as a starting point for exploring men's objectification perpetration. While valuable, such inductive approaches may miss important aspects of objectification that are perhaps less visible to women such as objectifying attitudes and beliefs that may or may not be conveyed through behaviors. The measure developed in the current work is novel in that it expands on

our understanding of men's objectification perpetration using a deductive approach built on theory.

Fortunately, there has been ample theorizing regarding the different facets of sexual objectification from objectification theorists and researchers. Nussbaum (1995) articulated seven ways that men objectify women including: instrumentality (i.e., treating women as a means toward a sexual end); denial of autonomy (i.e., treating women as lacking self-determination); inertness (i.e., treating women as lacking agency); fungibility (i.e., treating women as interchangeable with similar women); violability (i.e., treating women as lacking bodily integrity); ownership (i.e., treating women as property); and denial of subjectivity (i.e., treating women as lacking feelings). Langton (2009) expanded Nussbaum's (1995) typology, suggesting three additional facets of objectification: reduction to body (i.e., treating women as bodies); reduction to appearance (i.e., treating women in terms of their attractiveness); and silencing (i.e., treating women as lacking voice). Within the psychological literature, Morris et al. (2018; see also Morris & Goldenberg, 2015) recently theorized and found support for two forms of objectification—sex-based objectification (i.e., focusing on women's sexual features or functions), which is associated with animalistic dehumanization meaning that women perceived through this lens are seen as having more attributes in common with animals relative to humans, and appearance-focused objectification (i.e., focusing on women's beauty or physical appearance), which is associated with mechanistic dehumanization meaning that women perceived through this lens are seen as having more attributes in common with objects relative to humans. The theorization put forth by Morris et al. (2018) aligns with assertions from other objectification scholars (e.g., Roberts et al., 2018) who suggest that it may be important to distinguish between the broader concept of appearance-based objectification and sex-based objectification which lies at the intersection of objectification and sexualization. In summary, theorists have suggested that sexual objectification can manifest in the minds and behaviors of perceivers in myriad ways.

Development of the OPS (Research Question 1)

Given the connection between men's objectification perpetration and men's dehumanized perspectives of women, a deeper understanding of men's objectifying cognitions, motives, and behaviors is essential to stopping sexual violence. To that aim, we created the OPS as an instrument to assess men's objectifying cognitions and behaviors directed toward women. Based on theorizing about objectification perpetration, the OPS was developed by a panel of objectification experts to represent the typology of objectification articulated by Nussbaum (1995) and Langton (2009). That is, items were developed to map onto instrumentality, denial of autonomy, inertness, fungibility, violability, ownership, denial of subjectivity, body reduction, appearance reduction, and silencing of women. Because of the important distinction between sex-based and appearance-based objectification articulated by Morris et al. (2015, 2018; see also Langton, 2009), these items contained content focused on sexual body parts and functions as well as beauty and appearance more generally. And while previous research has focused on either cognitions (e.g., Other Objectification Questionnaire- Women; Objectified Body Consciousness Scale) or behaviors (e.g., Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale-Perpetrator), the OPS contains both objectifying beliefs as well as actions, so that the cognitive, motivational, and behavioral aspects of attitudes were represented within the same scale. Factor Structure of the OPS (Research Question 2)

We then explored the factor structure of the OPS to reduce items and to examine its psychometric properties. We aimed to include a sufficient number of items (i.e., 9–15 items per hypothesized factor; Clark & Watson, 1995) for identifying 10 discrete factors in line with theorizing from Nussbaum (1995) and Langton (2009). Although a 10-factor solution was plausible given the various dimensions previously identified in the literature (see similar amounts of items and factors for other gender measures like the Conformity to Masculine Norms Inventory; Mahalik et al., 2003), we also explored

whether there was a more parsimonious solution yielding fewer factors. It is possible that theorists distinguish between many possible manifestations of objectification, but that these various aspects are indistinguishable in the minds of perceivers (e.g., treating people as a means toward an end may be inextricably connected to seeing instrumental others as interchangeable with one another). Thus, we initially used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) as well as objectification theorizing (Langton, 2009; Morris et al., 2018; Nussbaum, 1995) to both consider the optimal factor structure balancing fit and parsimony while also reducing the number of items for ease of administration of the final scale.

Construct Validity of the OPS (Research Question 3)

Construct validation provides researchers with confidence that their measure does indeed assess the phenomenon of interest and has been argued to be a “fundamental methodology in the scientific process, particularly in psychology” (Flake et al., 2017, p. 370), where constructs of interest are often abstract in nature. In line with best practices suggested by Flake and colleagues, we examined construct validity of the OPS following three phases. While Study 1 involves a substantive phase in which development of items is theoretically driven (Research Question 1) and a structural phase in which demonstration of acceptable psychometric properties (Research Question 2), Study 2 relied upon an independent sample to confirm the factor structure found in Study 1 for the external phase in which convergent and divergent validity, in addition to predictive utility of the measure are assessed (Research Question 3). We examined construct validity for the OPS by exploring relations between composite scores from the final version of the OPS subscales and closely associated constructs derived from objectification theory and research, including a measure of interpersonal sexual objectification perpetration (ISOS-P; Gervais et al., 2018) and the unpublished Men’s Objectification of Women Scale (MOWS; Curran, 2004) that assesses objectifying attitudes, because recent research has found connections between scores on this scale and objectifying gazes (Bareket et al., 2019). We also examined associations between OPS scores and constructs not theorized in objectification theory (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997) but that have been linked to objectification perpetration, including sexual violence perpetration (Koss & Gidycz, 1985), sexual exchange endorsement (Rudman, 2017; Rudman & Fetterolf, 2014), and negative attitudes toward women (Wright & Tokunaga, 2016).

Study 1: Scale Development and EFA (Research Question 1)

The purpose of Study 1 was to develop the OPS for men and to conduct an initial examination of the factor structure.

Participants and Procedure

Participants were 609 men recruited to participate in a survey titled, “Perceptions of Situations, Other People, and Ourselves.” Two hundred seventy-one men were recruited using Amazon’s Mechanical Turk (MTurk), whereas 338 men were recruited through a psychology department participant pool at a large Midwestern university. As advertised on MTurk and the participant pool website, men aged 18 and older were invited to complete a survey online using their personal computer. MTurk workers were compensated with \$0.50 and students received course credit. Institutional review board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to study recruitment. Following informed consent, participants completed an online survey comprised of the OPS and demographic questions.

Data from 50 participants were excluded from analyses for participants’ failure to correctly respond to two of three attention checks administered within the survey (e.g., if you’re paying attention, please select “strongly disagree”), resulting in a final sample of 559 men (240 MTurk workers, 319 students).

Participants ranged in age from 17 to 86 and the average age of the sample was 25.64 ($SD = 9.95$). The majority of participants were Caucasian (418; 74.8%), followed by Hispanic (42; 7.5%), Asian (35; 7.5%), African American (31; 5.5%), and Native American (20; 3.6%). The majority identified as heterosexual (488; 87.3%), followed by bisexual (43; 7.7%), gay (19; 3.4%), or another sexual orientation (9; 1.6%). Moreover, the majority of participants self-identified as single (298; 53.3%), followed by in a self-defined committed relationship (120; 21.5%), married (107; 19.1%), in an open relationship (16; 2.9%), engaged (8; 1.4%), divorced (6; 1.1%), or another relationship status (3; .5%).

Development of the Objectification Perpetration Scale

The OPS was developed to assess men's cognitive and behavioral objectification of women. Three objectification experts generated items using a deductive approach in which the theoretical definition of objectification was used as a guideline (Hinkin, 1998). Specifically, the group relied on typologies of objectification developed by prominent objectification theorists (Langton, 2009; Nussbaum, 1995).

Conceptual Definitions

According to Nussbaum (1995, p. 257), someone perpetrates objectification when they are "treating as an object what is really not an object, what is, in fact, a human being." Following this definition, Nussbaum suggests seven manifestation of objectification in which the objectifier treats or perceives the target as: a tool for his purposes (*instrumentality*), lacking in autonomy and self-determination (*denial of autonomy*), lacking in agency and activity (*inertness*), interchangeable with similar others (*fungibility*), something that is permissible to physically harm (*violability*), something that can be owned, bought, or sold (*ownership*), or something whose experience and feeling (if any) need not be taken into account (*denial of subjectivity*). Relying on the same operational definition, Langton (2009) added three additional manifestations of objectification in which the objectifier treats or perceives the target as if: she is lacking the capability to speak (silencing), she is able to be represented by her body parts alone (focus on sexual body parts), or her worth is determined by her sex appeal (*focus on sexual appearance*).

Item Generation

Members of the investigative team developed items representative of the 10 dimensions based on past measurement of objectification perpetration (e.g., Curran, 2004; Kozee et al., 2007; Strelan & Hargreaves, 2005) and self-objectification (e.g., McKinley & Hyde, 1996). For each dimension, 9–15 items were developed for a total of 116 items. Several outside experts also evaluated the items and made suggestions for revisions and additions which resulted in a total of 140 items. We omitted reverse-coded items due to potential pitfalls (e.g., increased risk of response errors and contaminated factor structure) for a final item pool comprised of 120 items. A 5-point Likert response scale was used (i.e., 1 = *not at all*, 2 = *slightly*, 3 = *somewhat*, 4 = *moderately*, 5 = *extremely*).

Initial EFA

Responses to the 120-item pool were examined using EFA with robust maximum-likelihood estimation and an oblique rotation (geomin¹) which allowed for correlated factors. Scree plots of eigenvalues and parallel analysis for the 120 items suggested a two- or three- factor solution was the best fit

to the data (Brown, 2015); however, given the absence of a clear and parsimonious factor solution, and factors with poor content validity, we concluded that it was necessary to revisit the typologies represented within the item pool.

Revisiting Typologies Within the Item Pool

Nussbaum's (1995) typologies of objectification provided a sound starting point for item generation; however, the manifestations listed by Nussbaum are inclusive of all types of objectification (e.g., including how a boss may objectify a productive and useful employee). Given our aim to measure men's objectification of women to better predict when and why men engage in sexual aggression, we turned our attention to a more exclusive focus on sexual objectification that lies at the intersection of objectification and sexualization. Specifically, Morris and Goldenberg (2015) suggest that objectification is perpetrated when a woman is seen as less human either because the objectifier focuses exclusively on the target's beauty and physical *appearance* (beauty-based objectification) or on the target's *sexual body* parts and functions to the extent that they are seen as capable of representing them (sex-based objectification).² While objectifying behaviors and cognitions can be classified based on the typologies suggested by Nussbaum (1995) and Langton (2009), two behaviors or cognitions within the same typology could be further distinctly classified depending on the perpetrator's focus. For example, a behavior that would fulfill Langton's typology of ownership could either be sex (e.g., expecting a woman to provide a sexual favor in response to buying her dinner) or appearance-based (e.g., expecting a wife or girlfriend to do what it takes to remain attractive in their eyes). With this alternative conceptualization in mind, the three experts classified each of the 120 items into the following categories: appearance-based objectification, sex-based objectification, both appearance- and sex-based objectification, or neither appearance- nor sex-based objectification. Items that did not clearly distinguish between appearance versus sex-based objectification, or did not represent either dimension, were excluded. Interrater reliability between the three experts was 70.83% suggesting there was a good level of agreement in the characterization of items (Fleiss' fixed-marginal $\kappa = .54$, 95% CI [.45, .62]). The final set of 70 items included 38 items characterized as appearance-based objectification and 32 items characterized as sex-based objectification (the remaining 50 items were dropped). Next, the items representing the two theoretical dimensions suggested by Morris and Goldenberg (2015)—appearance-based and sex-based objectification—were examined with an EFA using an oblique (geomin) rotation. Similar to the previous EFA with the initial item pool, we examined scree plots and conducted a parallel analysis which suggested that a two-factor model was the best fit to the data. Additionally, nested model comparisons demonstrated that the two-factor model was superior to the one-factor model, $\chi^2(69) = 1841.43$, $p < .001$ and, based on indices of local fit (i.e., salience of factor loadings, absence of cross-loadings) and global fit, comparative fit index (CFI) = .954, Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) = .951, root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA) = .031 (95% CI [.029, .033]), a two-factor model was considered to be the best fit to the data. Please refer to the table in the Online Supplemental Materials for the full EFA solution of Study 1. Next, we closely reviewed the composition of each factor and retained items that had a significant ($p < .05$) and salient ($>.40$) factor loading to a given factor and loaded to that factor alone (i.e., no significant cross-loadings), resulting in the identification of 16 items loading to Factor 1 which appeared to uniquely represent sex-based objectification and eight items loading to Factor 2 which appeared to uniquely represent appearance-based objectification. Seven of those items (Item No.: 32, 53, 70, 103, 104, 126, 128) did not load on the expected factor based on theory (e.g., an item that was theorized to fit with sex-based objectification but loaded onto the appearance-based objectification factor), and those items were dropped. The panel of objectification experts also identified two items loading to the same dimension with a high degree of redundancy (Item No. 117: "I sometimes cannot help myself from looking at a

woman's body" and Item No. 134: "For me, it is hard not to gaze at women's breasts, waist, butt, or legs") as such we dropped the first item referring to woman's body in general (Item No. 117). The final item pool included an appearance-based objectification factor composed of 10 items and a sex-based objectification factor composed of six items. As a final step, we examined the pool of 16 items with EFA. As expected, items had significant and salient factor loadings on each respective factor (see Table 1)³ and the two factors had a large correlation with one another ($r = .65$).

Reliability of the OPS Scores

Items demonstrated excellent internal consistency for the appearance-based objectification subscale score ($\alpha = .85$) and sex-based objectification subscale score ($\alpha = .96$).

Study 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Construct Validity (Research Questions 2 and 3)

In Study 2, we conducted a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of the newly developed 16-item OPS with a sample of men from the community. Based on our final EFA findings in Study 1, we hypothesized that a two-factor model including appearance-based and sex-based objectification would be supported. We then evaluated the convergent validity of our new measure by examining correlations between the OPS and previously used measures of similar constructs of attitudes, cognitions, and behaviors related to objectification perpetration. Moreover, we evaluated the incremental predictive validity of the OPS by examining whether this measure predicted outcomes of interest above and beyond other existing measures of objectification perpetration.

Method

Participants and Procedure

Participants were 334 men recruited from Amazon's MTurk using the same procedures as Study 1. Data from participants who failed to correctly respond to two of five attention checks (e.g., to demonstrate you are paying attention, please select "strongly disagree") were excluded from analyses, resulting in a sample of 296 male participants. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 81 and the average age of the sample was 33.51 ($SD = 10.76$). The majority of participants were Caucasian (183; 61.8%), followed by African American (41; 13.9%), Asian/Pacific Islander (22; 7.4%), Hispanic (16; 5.4%), Native American (15; 5.1%), or another race or ethnicity (18; 6.08%). The majority of participants identified as heterosexual (208; 70.3%), followed by bisexual (66; 22.3%), or gay (4; 1.4%). Moreover, the majority of participants self-identified as married (114; 38.5%), followed by single (102; 53.3%), in a self-defined committed relationship (38; 12.8%), in an open relationship (11; 3.7%), engaged (6; 2.0%), or divorced (6; 2.0%).

Measures

Objectification Perpetration Scale. First, men were asked to complete the 16-item OPS created in Study 1, including the appearance-based (10 items) and sex-based (6 items) objectification subscales. Participants' scores were averaged (descriptive statistics for all measures can be found in Table 2), with higher scores indicating greater perpetration of objectification. Items were internally consistent among each of the subscales (alphas and omegas of all measures can be found in Table 2) and the scale as a whole.

Additional Objectification Perpetration Measures. Next, participants completed the two published measures of interpersonal sexual objectification perpetration as well as one unpublished measure. To

assess the frequency of men’s perpetration of objectifying behaviors, participants completed the Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale-Perpetrator (ISOS-P; Gervais et al., 2018; see Kozee et al., 2007, for original scale). This 15-item measure assesses the frequency with which people engage in body evaluations (BE; e.g., “How often have you made inappropriate sexual comments about someone’s body?”) and unwanted sexual advances (USA; e.g., “How often have you touched or fondled someone against her will?”), using a 1 (*never*) to 5 (*almost always*) scale. Participants’ responses were averaged, with higher scores indicating more frequent perpetration of objectifying behaviors toward women. As Table 2 shows, like in past use of this measure (e.g., Gervais et al., 2018; $\alpha_{total} = .83$), internal consistency was good for the scale and each of the subscales.

Table 1

Items, Factor Loadings, Community Estimates, Corrected Item–Total Correlations, Means, and Standard Deviations for Each Objectification Perpetration Factor Obtained in Study 1

Factor and item	Factor 1	Factor 2	h^2	Item/Total r	M	SD
Factor 1: Sex-based objectification						
1. It is sometimes okay for me to manipulate women to have sex with them.	.896	.014	.80	.84	1.70	1.21
3. During sexual encounters, I don’t think much about my partner’s thoughts or feelings.	.768	.070	.59	.004	1.80	1.25
4. Using a sex toy is basically the same as having sex with a woman.	.859	–.090	.75	.73	1.72	1.20
5. During sex, I like women to lie still until I’m finished.	.930	–.074	.87	.81	1.69	1.19
6. It is unpleasant when women talk during sexual encounters.	.793	.064	.63	.80	1.79	1.22
7. I ask my sexual partner to not talk about her feelings if she thinks it will cause troubles in my sexual life.	.862	.014	.74	.82	1.70	1.21
8. It is not a big deal if a woman gets hurt when I’m trying to get her to have sex with me.	.850	–.075	.73	.74	1.66	1.21
9. There are situations when it is ok for me to use coercion on a woman to have sex with her.	.888	–.030	.79	.81	1.69	1.19
10. There are situations when it is okay for me to use physical constraint on a woman to have sex with her.	.876	–.037	.77	.80	1.73	1.20
11. It is reasonable to expect that if I pay for dinner, a woman will pay me	.844	.075	.72	.84	1.72	1.25

back with a sexual favor.

Factor 2: Appearance-based objectification

2. Whether a woman is attractive or not depends on what I think.	.081	.520	.28	.50	2.62	1.43
12. I expect that my girlfriend or wife will do her best to remain attractive in my eyes.	.008	.655	.43	.53	2.61	1.28
13. I quickly and easily sort women in my mind as more or less attractive.	.021	.753	.57	.62	2.66	1.30
14. I rate women's attractiveness based on her sexual body parts (e.g., breast, butt).	.064	.717	.52	.63	2.60	1.25
15. For me, it is hard not to gaze at women's breasts, waist, butt, or legs.	.007	.735	.54	.58	2.45	1.34
16. I like when women wear clothing that draws attention to their body.	.020	.666	.44	.54	2.81	1.24

Note. Items were rated on a scale from 1 (*not at all*) to 5 (*extremely*). $N = 559$. Highest factor loadings for each item are shown in boldface.

Table 2*Means, Standard Deviations, Alphas, and Intercorrelations of the Measures in Study 2*

Measure	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range	ω	α	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. OPS total	2.53	1.07	1.00–4.75	.96	.96	—									
2. OPS-SO	2.24	1.25	1.00–4.80	.97	.97	.96*	—								
3. OPS-AO	3.01	1.01	1.00–5.00	.88	.88	.84*	.67*	—							
4. MOWS	3.08	0.89	1.00–4.78	.94	.94	.80*	.72*	.79*	—						
5. ISOS total	2.45	1.05	1.00–4.73	.97	.96	.93*	.93*	.72*	.78*	—					
6. ISOS BE	2.57	1.00	1.00–4.73	.95	.94	.91*	.89*	.76*	.81*	.99*	—				
7. ISOS USA	2.13	1.28	1.00–4.75	.92	.94	.89*	.93*	.59*	.67*	.95*	.89*	—			
8. OOQ-W	–1.49	11.51	1.25–6.38	—	—	–.10	–.20*	.14*	.13*	–.12*	–.06	–.23*	—		
9. Misogyny	1.92	0.89	1.00–4.00	.94	.94	.77*	.80*	.54*	.66*	.78*	.75*	.78*	–.11	—	
10. SES-P	3.33	2.43	1.00–6.00	—	—	.76*	.79*	.52*	.60*	.77*	.75*	.77*	–.12	.69*	—
11. SEES	3.77	1.54	1.00–6.67	.94	.93	.84*	.82*	.68*	.81*	.82*	.80*	.80*	–.08	.75*	.67*

Note. *N* = 296. OPS = Objectification Perpetration Scale; OPS-SO = sex-based subscale of the OPS; OPS-AO = appearance-based subscale of the OPS; MOWS = Men's Objectification of Women Scale; ISOS = Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale; ISOS BE = body evaluation subscale of the ISOS; ISOS USA = Unwanted Sexual Advances subscale of the ISOS; OOQ-W = Other-Objectification Questionnaire of Women; SES-P = Sexual Experiences Survey— Perpetrator form; SEES = Sexual Exchange Endorsement Scale.

* *p*

Additionally, participants completed the OOO-W (Strelan & Hargreaves, 2005), an adaptation of the SOQ (Noll & Fredrickson, 1998). The Other-Objectification Questionnaire (OOQ-W) asks participants to rank the importance of five observable physical appearance attributes (i.e., weight, physical attractiveness, muscular definition, measurements, sex appeal) relative to five nonobservable physical attributes (i.e., strength, energy, health, fitness, coordination) when evaluating women on a 1 (*most important*) to 10 (*least important*) rank order scale. Rankings of observable and nonobservable attributes were separately summed, and other-objectification scores were calculated by subtracting nonobservable scores from observable scores. Scores can range from -25 to 25, with higher scores indicating more other objectification. Because items on the OOO-W are rank ordered and therefore dependent on one another, traditional indicators of reliability are uninformative (Calogero et al., 2011; Hill & Fischer, 2008). However, confirming that the scale was completed and scored correctly, there was a perfect linear relation between observable and nonobservable scores ($r = 1.00, p < .001$), as expected with the rank ordering.

Participants also completed the MOWS (Curran, 2004). While unpublished, previous work has connected scores on this measure to the perpetration of objectifying behaviors including sexualized gazing (Bareket et al., 2019). This 18-item measure asks participants to rate their agreement to statements like, “The first thing I notice about a woman is her body” using a 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*) scale. Participants’ responses were averaged, with higher scores indicating greater objectification of women. Similar to other uses of this measure (Bareket et al., 2019; $\alpha = .88$), the internal consistency of this measure was high.

Correlates of Objectification Perpetration. In addition to measures of objectification, participants completed several measures that while connected to objectification, are conceptually distinct, including misogynistic attitudes, sexual assault perpetration, and sexual exchange endorsement. Specifically, to assess the extent to which men felt hatred or strong prejudice against women, participants completed a measure of misogyny (Fleming et al., 2018). This 6-item measure asks men to rate their agreement with statements including, “In my opinion, women are bad news.” and “I avoid women except when it comes to sex.” using a 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 4 (*strongly agree*) scale. Responses were averaged, with higher scores indicating more misogynistic attitudes toward women. Similar to past use of this measure (e.g., Fleming et al., 2018; $\alpha = .78$), the scale revealed adequate reliability.

Participants were asked to report on the number of times they had perpetrated unwanted sexual acts using the Sexual Experiences Survey—Perpetrator form (SES-P; Koss et al., 2007). This measure first asks participants to report on the number of times they have relied on various tactics (e.g., taking advantage of someone when they were too drunk or out of it to know what was happening; telling lies, threatening to end the relationship) to perpetrate four forms of sexual assault (e.g., inserting their penis or fingers into a woman’s vagina), and then to report on the number of times they attempted to rely on various tactics to try to perpetrate the same four forms of sexual assault. Response options included: 0 times, 1 time, 2 times, 3 times, or more than 3 times. We used nonredundant scores, meaning that a participant’s sexual assault perpetration is coded only by the category of his most severe type (Davis et al., 2014). Relying on a nonredundant scoring system reflects a continuum of “objective severity” of assault perpetration ranging from least serious (no perpetration) to most serious (completed rape; Koss et al., 2007). As a result, participants were classified in six categories: nonperpetrators, sexual contact perpetration, attempted coercion, perpetrated coercion, attempted rape, and rape perpetration. Previous empirical evidence supports the use of the SES-P for assessing sexual aggression perpetration, showing high internal consistency ($\alpha = .89$), test–retest reliability, and validity (Koss & Gidycz, 1985).

To assess the extent to which participants endorsed the sexist ideology that women exchange sex with men for resources, participants completed the Sexual Exchange Endorsement Scale (SEES; Fetterolf & Rudman, 2017). This 9-item scale asks participants to rate the extent to which they agree with statements regarding the sexual exchange between men and women including, “A reason there are fewer marriages today is because women no longer insist on holding out for an engagement ring before having sex.” and “Women strive to be sexually attractive primarily to get men to provide for them.” using a 1

(*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly disagree*) Likert scale. Responses were averaged, with higher scores indicating greater beliefs that women exchange sex for resources; as in previous uses of this measure (Fetterolf & Rudman, 2017; $\alpha = .83$), the measure revealed strong reliability.

Results

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The hypothesized two-factor model demonstrated excellent global fit (CFI = .97; TLI = .97; RMSEA = .05; standardized root-mean-square residual [SRMR] = .03, $\chi^2 = 187.94$, $p < .001$). Factor loadings for each item were significant ($p < .001$) on the expected factor, and factor loadings ranged from .81 to .90 for the appearance-focused factor and .58 to .83 for the sex-focused factor. This two-factor model demonstrated superior fit (Akaike information criterion [AIC] = 12,376.434; Bayesian information criterion [BIC] = 12,557.261) relative to a one-factor model (AIC = 12,714.559; BIC = 12,891.696; CFI = .885; TLI = .868; RMSEA = .11; SRMR = .08) as evidenced by smaller BIC and AIC values. Additionally, there was a relatively high correlation between the two factors ($r = .73$); however, this correlation was below .80 suggesting that these dimensions of objectification perpetration are related, but that subscale scores demonstrate adequate discriminant validity (Brown, 2015).

To further examine dimensionality of the measure, we tested a symmetrical bifactor model with all items loading to a general (g) factor, the appearance-focused items loading to a specific factor, and the sex-focused items loading to a specific factor (Reise et al., 2010). Factors were set to be orthogonal (i.e., covariances are fixed to zero). In a symmetrical bifactor model, the variance of each item is split between (a) the g factor, (b) the corresponding specific factor, and (c) measurement error (i.e., variance not explained by the g or specific factor). The symmetrical model led to an inadmissible solution with the *appearance-focused* factor collapsing (i.e., *non-positive definite* residual covariance matrix; factor loadings were nonsignificant; all but one-factor loadings were less than .30; negative residual variance for one item). This is not uncommon with symmetrical bifactor models (e.g., Panayiotou et al., 2020) and points to a substantial amount of the variance in the appearance-focused items shifting to the g factor. This is consistent with our conceptualization that appearance-focused objectification is more general in nature, whereas sex-based objectification represents the intersection of objectification and sexualization that women so often experience.

This led us to respecify as a bifactor S-1 model such that the appearance-focused items became reference items loading directly to the g

factor (and only the *g* factor), whereas the sex-based items loaded to both the *g* factor and a specific factor. In the context of the S-1 model, the *g* factor now represents the content of the reference

items—appearance-focused objectification perpetration—whereas the specific factor represents sex-based objectification perpetration *unique from* appearance-focused objectification. The bifactor S-1 model demonstrated excellent global fit, CFI = .97; TLI = .97; RMSEA = .05; SRMR = .03, $\chi^2(94) = 170.21, p < .001$. Factor loadings across all 16 items ranged from .56 to .83 for the “*g*” factor (now representing appearance-focused objectification). Factor loadings for the specific sex-based item ranged from .51 to .63. Despite the excellent fit of the S-1 model, it did not demonstrate superior fit (AIC = 12,377.449; BIC = 12,591.489) relative to a two-factor model (AIC = 12,376.434; BIC = 12,557.261).

Convergent and Incremental Predictive Validity

After confirming the factor structure of the OPS, we computed average scores for each subscale and examined the construct validity of those scores. First, we assessed whether scores on the Objectification Perpetration subscales were correlated with existing measures of objectification perpetration, including objectifying cognitions (OOQ-W; Strelan & Hargreaves, 2005), objectifying behaviors (ISOS-P; Gervais et al., 2018), and objectifying attitudes (MOWS; Curran, 2004). Second, we examined whether subscale scores were correlated with measures that are theoretically relevant, but conceptually distinct from objectification perpetration, including misogyny, sexual assault perpetration, and sexual exchange ideology. Finally, we explored whether subscale scores predicted these theoretically relevant outcomes beyond other measures of objectification perpetration (i.e., OOQ-W, ISOS-P, and MOWS).

Consistent with our hypotheses, scores on the sex-based and appearance-based subscales of the OPS were positively and strongly associated with scores on the ISOS-P and the MOWS. There was also a positive, though weak, relation between the

appearance-based subscale of the OPS and the OOQ-W, as predicted. Contrary to expectations, the OOQ-W although weak was negatively

Hierarchical Multiple Regression Analyses Illustrating the Incremental Variance in the Criteria Accounted for by Appearance-Based and Sex-Based Scores on the Objectification

B	Sexual exchange						Sexual experiences					
	Step 1			Step 2			Step 1			Step 2		
	B	t	B	t	B	t	B	t	B	t	B	t
.88	.09	9.67***	.88	.10	9.08***	-.22	.19	-.19	-.10	.21	-.50	
.60	.08	7.88***	.00	.13	-.002	1.92	.16	12.22***	.94	.26	3.58***	4.87***
			-.006	.004	-1.34				.01	.01	-1.44	
									.60			
									.59			
												.63

Δ Objectification of Women Scale; ISOS-P = Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale; OOQ-W = Other-Objectification Questionnaire of Women; OPS = Objectification Perpetration

= appearance-based subscale of the OPS.

related to the sex-based subscale of the OPS¹. It is possible that the OQW assesses appearance-based objectification similar to the appearance subscale of the OPS¹ but does not tap into sex-based objectification. We return to this issue in the General Discussion section. The subscales of the OPS were also connected to measures of constructs that are distinct, but conceptually connected to objectification perpetration, evidenced by strong positive correlations that emerged between the subscales and misogyny, sexual assault perpetration, and sexual exchange ideology (see Table 2).

Finally, given that there are already existing measures of objectification perpetration in the literature, we examined whether scores on each subscale of the OPS significantly predicted misogyny, sexual assault perpetration, and sexual exchange ideology, beyond existing measures. Specifically, we conducted three separate hierarchical multiple regressions with misogyny, sexual assault perpetration, and sexual exchange ideology as the outcomes. For each of these regressions, the existing perpetration measures, the OQW, the ISOS-P, and the MOWS, were entered at Step 1 and the sex-based and appearance-based subscales of the OPS were entered at Step 2. When each subscale is simultaneously included in the model, scores on the sex-based objectification subscale of the OPS predicted unique variance in misogyny scores, sexual assault perpetration, and sexual exchange endorsement, whereas scores on the appearance-based objectification subscale of the OPS predicted unique variance in misogyny alone and in the reverse direction of scores on the sex-

Table 3

Criterion	Misogyny				
	Step 1		Step 2		
Predictor	B	t	B	t	
MOWS	.11	.07	1.69	.21	2.84**
ISOS-P	.57	.06	10.06***	.20	2.12*
OQW				.003	.99
OPS-SB					5.48***
OPS-AO					-2.89***
R ²					.61
Adjusted R ²					.61
					²

Note. MOWS = Men'

based objectification subscale (see Table 3). Across analyses, the subscale scores on the OPS uniquely predicted the theorized outcomes, suggesting that scores on the OPS are connected to, but empirically distinct from, related measures of sexual objectification.

Discussion

In recent years, the objectification literature has expanded beyond the focus on consequences among women experiencing objectification addressed in the original objectification theory paper (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997) to explore what leads individuals to perpetrate objectification in the first place. This is an important development because identifying the predictors of perpetration could be the key to reducing objectification perpetration and its negative consequences for women, but validated measures of objectification perpetration are necessary to support this theoretical extension. While researchers have adapted previously validated measures to assess men's perpetration of objectifying behaviors (ISOS-P; Gervais et al., 2018) and cognitions (OOQ-W; Strelan & Hargreaves, 2005) based on women's reported experiences of objectification and self-objectification, the current work developed and validated a new measure, the OPS, specifically to assess perpetration of men's objectifying behaviors, motivations, and cognitions derived from theories and models that focus on objectification *perpetration* (Langton, 2009; Morris & Goldenberg, 2015; Nussbaum, 1995).

In Study 1, results revealed that the OPS has two related factors: the first factor assesses the extent to which men objectify women through a focus on women as sexualized objects and the second factor assesses the extent to which men focus on women's physical appearance. Study 2 used an independent sample to confirm the factor structure found in Study 1 and was also used to demonstrate convergent and discriminant validity of the sex- and appearance- based subscale scores from the OPS. The results of a series of CFAs in Study 2 suggest that a focus on two factors is warranted. First, a two-factor model was superior to a single-factor model. Second, a collapsed symmetric bifactor model respecified as a S-1 bifactor model with appearance-based items serving as a reference to the g factor also provided excellent fit. Together, these two findings point to the utility of considering sex-based objectification and appearance-based objectification separately with the possibility that appearance-based objectification is more general in nature, whereas sex-based objectification is more specific. This reveals the nuanced intersection between women's experiences of objectification that are sexualizing.

In Study 2, scores on the OPS were strongly positively correlated with men's objectifying attitudes as measured by the MOWS, and the perpetration version of the ISOS, in addition to related attitudes including sexual exchange beliefs, misogynistic attitudes, and even perpetration of sexual assault. Interestingly, while there was a weak positive correlation between the woman version of the OOQ and the

appearance-based subscale of the OPS, there was a weak negative correlation between the woman version of the OOQ and the sex-based subscale of the OPS. This finding may suggest that sex-based objectification assessed by the OPS is a markedly different construct than the appearance-based objectification encompassed within the woman version of the OOQ. In the woman version of the OOQ, participants rank order the importance of appearance- (e.g., body measurements) relative to competency- (e.g., energy level) based physical attributes in women. Although objectified women are perceived as lacking in competence (Heflick et al., 2011; Heflick & Goldenberg, 2009; Wollast et al., 2018), it is possible that competence-based attributes assessed in the woman version of the OOQ (e.g., stamina, coordination, physical fitness) may also play an important role in men's perceived ability to use women as objects in achieving their sexual desires. If true, this would suggest that the OOQ-W could possibly be a reliable measure of appearance-based objectification that fails to measure the nuances involved in sex-based objectification. Yet, it is important to note that while a commonly relied on measure within the literature, the woman version of the OOQ has never been validated and has been criticized for the confusion created by the rank order scaling and statistical concerns with interpretation (see Calogero, 2011; Wollast et al., 2021). Past criticisms paired with the fact that scores on the woman version of the OOQ were not associated with

other variables within Study 2 in an expected way (e.g., inverse or no correlation with the ISOS-P), highlight the necessity for a validated measure like the OPS.

Moreover, Study 2 provided evidence that the OPS has incremental predictive validity, allowing for substantial improvements in the prediction of negative outcomes (i.e., sexual aggression perpetration, sexual exchange endorsement, and negative attitudes toward women) above and beyond other objectification measures. Sex-based objectification as measured by the OPS predicts misogynistic attitudes toward women, endorsement of the sexist ideology regarding women's ability to exchange sex for resources, and sexual aggression, beyond existing measures of sexual objectification perpetration. Appearance-based objectification as measured by the OPS predicts misogynistic attitudes toward women beyond the existing measures of sexual objectification perpetration. Interestingly, scores on the sex-based objectification subscale of the OPS predicted higher levels of misogyny, as expected; yet, scores on the appearance-based objectification subscale of the OPS and misogynistic attitudes toward women were mixed. At the bivariate level, appearance-based objectification and misogyny were positively correlated, as expected. However, when controlling for sex-based objectification at the multivariate level, more appearance-based objectification appeared to predict less misogyny. Because the latter finding was unexpected and was in opposite direction, it should be interpreted with caution, as it may be an artifact of controls in the multivariate analysis. At the same time, these results suggest that even though both subscales of the OPS are highly correlated ($r = .67$), there are conceptual differences between them. More sex-based objectification may be related to more misogyny, but when sex-based objectification is controlled for, more appearance-based objectification may be associated with more positive (or at least less negative) impressions of women. Importantly, subjectively positive impressions of women can still be sexist (e.g., benevolent sexism is associated with a range of sexist perceptions of women; Glick & Fiske, 1996). Similar to a Madonna-Whore dichotomy of perceiving women (Bareket et al., 2019), men's objectifying perspectives of women may result in distinct impressions of women depending on whether they are being reduced to, and evaluated on, their sex appeal or their appearance more broadly, but may still be sexist. The difference in predictive utility between the subscales is further support of the need to distinguish between different objectified processing of women; while sex-based objectification predicts sexual behaviors directed toward women, appearance-based objectification appears to predict more general attitudes about relations with women.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

Feminist philosophers suggest that objectification manifests in a number of ways. From a theoretical point of view, the results from the current work did not support the 10 factors theorized by Nussbaum (i.e., fungibility, denial of subjectivity, inertness, denial of autonomy, violability, instrumentality, and ownership; 1995) and Langton (i.e., silencing, focus on the sexual body parts, and focus on the sexual appearance;

2009). Instead, the development and validation of the OPS suggests that men's objectification of women reduces to focusing on either women's appearance or their sexual functions (Morris & Goldenberg, 2015). Although our EFA suggested two instead of 10 factors, it is possible that these 10 dimensions are present within perpetration of objectification, but that there is significant overlap among them.⁴ For example, instrumentality, fungibility, and focus on women's sex appeal are likely not mutually exclusive; men who perceive women as tools in achieving their sexual goals may therefore see women as interchangeable objects, such that any attractive woman would suffice, and as a result may connect to men reducing women to their sexual appearance.

Although a two-factor CFA model was ultimately the best fit to the data, the two factors were highly correlated with one another. Further, a S-1 bifactor model demonstrated excellent fit, suggesting that: (a) the appearance-based objectification subscale may be reflective of a general, underlying dimension of objectification perpetration and (b) the sex-based subscale represents a more specific and unique dimension of perpetration that not only objectifies women but sexualizes them as well. Together, these results suggest that researchers can confidently use the subscale scores in future research. At this point, however, researchers should proceed cautiously with using and interpreting a total score. The results from the S-1 bifactor model suggest that in addition to capturing appearance-focused objectification, the appearance-based subscale score might represent a general, underlying dimension of objectification perpetration. Thus, researchers interested in general objectification might use the appearance-based subscale rather than the total score. At the same time, while the same pattern of results emerged between the total score and correlates of objectification as well as the appearance-based subscale score and these correlates, the correlations differed in magnitude, suggesting that the total score and subscale score may be related, but represent different constructs (see Table 2). Plus, like any findings, replication of bifactor models with separate samples is useful. Therefore, we can recommend that people use the subscale scores, but future research (both theoretical and statistical) is needed to determine the utility of the total score. Just as sex-based and appearance-based objectification were highly correlated, yet had different predictive functions, these components may simultaneously encourage other forms of objectification. In line with this possibility, item generation posed a challenge when categorizing a suggested item as one dimension versus another. Because items were generated for each of the 10 dimensions, after the EFA we were able to see how items from these dimensions fell into the sex-based or appearance-based factors. Items generated to assess instrumentality, denial of subjectivity, inertness, violability, and silencing fell within the sex-based factor, whereas items generated to assess denial of autonomy, focus on the appearance, and focus on the sexual body parts fell into the appearance-based factor. Items generated to assess ownership, however, fell into both factors depending on whether the focus was on the "owner" of the beauty (e.g., I expect that my girlfriend or wife will do her best to remain attractive in my eyes; appearance-based factor) or the "recipient" who benefits from owning a woman (e.g., It is reasonable to expect that if I pay for dinner, a woman will pay me back with a sexual favor; sex-based factor). This suggests that even though the underlying purpose of the objectification is similar, the focus of the objectification is what shapes how these objectifying attitudes manifest.

In line with this idea, Morris et al. (2018; see also Morris & Goldenberg, 2015) highlighted the importance of distinguishing between two similar kinds of objectification, linking each to different forms of dehumanization. In particular, Morris and colleagues suggest objectification is either appearance or sexually focused. Results from a series of studies revealed that focusing on women's appearance led perceivers to deny female targets human nature, or in other words increased mechanistically dehumanizing perceptions; whereas focusing on women's sexuality led perceivers to deny female targets human uniqueness, or in other words increased animalistically dehumanizing perceptions. The development of the OPS supports Morris's theorizing of a two-factor structure of objectification perpetration. While Morris and colleagues found a link between

appearance-focused objectification and diminished perceptions of women's ability to feel pain, the sex-based, but not appearance-based, objectification subscale of the OPS predicted sexual aggression. This difference may be a result of perceiver's focus, or lack of focus, on female target's pain during instances of sexual aggression. Additionally, while Morris et al. (2018) manipulated sex-focus and appearance-focus orthogonally, our study found that they are highly correlated, which may suggest that objectification is often both appearance- and sex-based rather than one or the other. These observations may be useful starting points as future researchers further explore what could be driving this inconsistency.

From a practical point of view, improving our understanding of the predictors of sexual aggression perpetration is valuable for preventing it. The current work reveals that the OPS is a useful tool for identifying men who perpetrate not only sexual objectification but also in predicting more extreme forms of aggression including sexual assault perpetration. Furthermore, results of the OPS revealed two distinct factors of objectification perpetration, suggesting that social interventions aimed at reducing sexual assault should be focused on emphasizing women's humanness *and* competence. Furthermore, given that appearance-focused objectification and sex-focused objectification emerged as separate factors, it would behoove practitioners who are developing interventions to prevent men's sexual objectification of women to focus on decreasing men's focus on women's sexual functions and appearance.

This instrument might convey useful information for clinicians and counselors; early identification of potential sexual abusers

would allow for more effective prevention efforts and educational programs. For example, the OPS may be considered a useful indicator for assessing the concomitant occurrence of sexual assault by potential sex offenders among forensic psychologists aiming for early detection methods in attempts to reduce recidivism. Relatedly, the OPS might be fruitful for counseling and clinical professionals working with men who struggle to form healthy relationships with women by identifying objectifying cognitions and attitudes. For clinicians working with perpetrators of intimate partner violence, the OPS may provide important insight into male patients' perceptions of women as sex objects that ultimately set the foundation for violence. Moreover, the OPS may be useful in educational contexts to assist educators in identification of potential abusers, as well as provide a deeper understanding of men's nuanced objectifying cognitions, motivations, and behaviors. Beyond perpetration, providing psychologists with a greater understanding of men's perpetration of objectification may even help shed light on how to provide care to women who are recipients of objectification (e.g., by helping women cope and combat both appearance-based and sex-based objectification).

Limitations and Future Directions

In the current work, we conducted a substantive review of previous literature to create items that mapped on with theoretical conceptualizations, provided evidence of structural validity through factor analysis, and finally in the external phase, we demonstrated that scores on the OPS have both convergent and discriminant validity. Although we relied on methods identified as best practices within construct validation (Flake et al., 2017), our work is not without limitations. For instance, our initial item pool involved items that were developed to map on to the 10 objectification typologies outlined by both Nussbaum (1995) and Langton (2009), but we determined the best-fitting model was one involving only two typologies. While we do think that it is possible that men's objectification of women, at its core, is merely divisible into whether the evaluation of women is sex- or appearance-based, it is possible that the supported two-factor structure could be an artifact of the way in which items were worded during the item generation phase. In other words, the lack of support for a 10-factor structure does not suggest that Nussbaum and Langton's typologies are incorrect; instead, it suggests that the OPS is better suited at assessing objectification that falls into appearance or sex focus. Nonetheless, future research examining the dimensionality of the OPS is required to investigate the structure of objectification perpetration. In future attempts to develop and refine measures of objectification perpetration, we hope that researchers continue to examine methods for assessing the various typologies of objectification suggested by Nussbaum and Langton.

There are currently also limits to our understanding of the OPS's utility. For instance, the current work relied on samples of men who completed the scale with women as the focal target of perpetrated objectification. While the OPS is not gender neutral like some previously relied upon measures (e.g., ISOS-P; Gervais et al., 2018), these measures have been found to lack gender invariance despite this; the majority of objectification behaviors have been found to be directed by men toward women. Based on this previous empirical data and on the theoretical consideration of objectification as a tool to maintain and reinforce patriarchy (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997), we created a measure to specifically assess men's objectification of women. It is important, however, to be aware that other kinds of objectification may occur (i.e.,

from men toward men, or nonbinary or transgender people, and from women to other women) and for researchers to develop and validate objectification perpetration measures connected to these additional intersections of identity (Crenshaw, 1989). Additionally, the inclusion of the subscale scores on the OPS to the model in Study 2, while significant, did not result in a large R^2 change. While sex- and appearance-based scores on the OPS did explain a significant amount of variance above and beyond previous measures of objectification, it is possible there are other factors alongside these scores that should be considered when predicting sexist ideologies and sexual aggression.

Moreover, further investigation of the dimensionality and structure of objectification perpetration is warranted. Specifically, the EFA and CFA results suggested that the two-factor model was superior to the one-factor model and the two factors demonstrated discriminant validity; however, a collapsed bifactor model and respecified S-1 model, which demonstrated excellent fit, suggested that the appearance-based items might reflect a more general dimension of objectification perpetration, whereas sex-based perpetration might represent a specific type of objectification.

Further, it is important for future research to explore the unique outcomes of each dimension of objectification perpetration including other related cognitions, motives, and behaviors (e.g., intimate relationship satisfaction). Given the lack of previously validated measures of objectification perpetration, this seems like an especially fertile avenue for future research. Similarly, a deeper understanding of men's objectification perpetration may also allow researchers to develop new measures or manipulations of sex- and appearance-based objectification, which would provide further insight into whether these differences in objectification perpetration have differential outcomes for women targets.

Conclusion

The OPS consists of 16 items with two factors: appearance-based objectification (composed of 10 items) and sex-based objectification (composed of 6 items). In line with the theoretical proposition of Morris et al. (2018), sex- and appearance-based objectification are highly correlated; yet these two forms of objectification are distinguishable. Building on a burgeoning literature on objectification, and dehumanization more broadly, we recommend the use of the OPS as a holistic measure that assesses both cognitive, motivational, and behavioral perpetration of objectification,

that is, both sex- and appearance-based.

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